

RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF THE GROWTH OF MANURE CROPS IN THE REGIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Annotation

This article presents the results of phenological observations and analysis after sowing green manure crops. In this case, when analyzing the mung bean crop by variants, the fastest 50% germination was 8 days, 10 days for the sorghum crop, and 6 days for the soybean crop.

Key words: green manure crops, soil fertility, agrochemical analysis, humus, N-nitrogen, P-phosphorus, K-potassium, leguminous crops, green manure.

In developed countries of the world, scientific research is being conducted aimed at obtaining environmentally friendly, high-quality crop yields, preserving and increasing soil fertility, and improving the melioration state of lands through scientifically based crop rotation systems. Along with this, crops are grown in crop rotation in various soil and climatic conditions of our country, and now, to obtain high and quality yields of agricultural crops, preserve and increase soil fertility, and improve the melioration state of lands, the introduction of cotton, winter wheat, legumes, and oilseeds into crop rotation systems is one of the urgent tasks.

According to Negmatov and Shavkatov [2], in the takyrl-like soils of the Kashkadarya region, when mung bean was sown early (20-30 June) with 14 kg of seeds per hectare for winter wheat stubble, the number of tubers formed per plant root averaged 24.

Studies have also shown that the formation of tuber mass in the roots of leguminous crops depends on sowing dates and planting depth. Shukurillayev G.Sh. [3].

With the use of green manure, favorable conditions are created for the reproduction and development of earthworms, as a result of which soil aeration improves and moisture is better preserved. Kenjaev, [1].

Corn is considered one of the most important grain crops and has food, fodder, technical, and agricultural significance. Seeds germinate with a single

embryonic root, which branches rapidly from germination to the formation of 3-4 leaves, forming a large number of lateral roots covered with root hairs. The embryonic rootlet absorbs water and nutrients from the soil until true roots appear and is preserved until the end of the plant's life. After 4-8 days of emergence, the tillering node forms and the formation of secondary roots occurs, resembling an embryonic rootlet in appearance.

From the lower nodes of the underground part of the stem, air roots or supporting roots appear, ensuring the plant's strength and serving as an additional source of nutrition. Corn roots penetrate to a depth of 180-190 cm, more than half of the root mass is located in the 0-20 cm layer. Early-ripening varieties have 5-10 internodes, late-ripening varieties have 20-25 internodes; their length is 1-2 cm at the base of the stem and up to 40 cm at the top.

In our experiment, after the completion of pre-sowing plowing, harrowing, and tillage of green manure crops, corn, soybeans, and mung beans were sown on July 19. In the analyses studied by variants, the 50% germination rate of sorghum on the ground was 11 days in the first variant, 13 days in the fourth variant, and 10 days in the seventh variant. It was established that in the seventh variant, sorghum germinated 3 days earlier than in the first and fourth variants in terms of surface germination.

Table 1

50% germination of corn, soybeans, mung beans

№	Options	50% Germination					
		25.07	27.07	29.07	31.07	Date	Germination period days
1	Corn	76	102	160	252	29.07	11
2	Soybean	203	408	565	663	26.07	8
3	mung bean	52	108	145	232	30.07	12
4	Corn	56	114	145	160	31.07	13
5	Soybean	205	436	578	645	26.07	8
6	mung bean	65	118	168	247	28.07	10
7	Corn	59	107	168	264	28.07	10
8	Soybean	456	602	703	780	25.07	6
9	mung bean	86	162	212		26.07	8

20°C heat is required for soybean seeds to ripen. Sprouts appear in 6-7 days at 19-22°C; 15-17 °C in 12 days. When the temperature rises from 10°C to 33°C, the duration of "growing-flowering" decreases from 45 days to 21 days. With repeated planting, the "growing-flowering" period is sharply reduced. Flowering

and fruit formation can occur at an interval of 11.5-27 °C. However, the optimal temperature is 21-23°C. The sum of effective temperatures is 1700-3500°C.

In the analyses studied by variants, the 50% germination rate of soybeans on the ground was 8 days in the second and fifth variants and 6 days in the eighth variant. In terms of soybean germination, in the eighth variant, compared to the second and fifth variants, germination was 2 days earlier.

Mung bean improves soil fertility, nitrogen-fixing bacteria accumulate in its roots during the growing season. During the growing season, under favorable weather conditions, it can accumulate up to 200 kg of nitrogen per hectare. Therefore, it is recommended to leave the mung bean roots in the ground and plow the land.

As a result of observations, when studying the germination of mung bean from green manure to the surface by 50%, in the third variant it was 12 days, in the sixth variant it was 10 days, and in the ninth variant it was 8 days. In this case, compared to the third and sixth variants, in the ninth variant, 50% of the seedlings appeared on the ground 2-4 days earlier. It was established that in the seventh variant, sorghum germinated 3 days earlier than in the other variants, and in the eighth variant, soybeans germinated 2 days earlier than in the second and fifth variants.

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